

SOCIAL SCIENCES

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE TURNOVER IN THE LABOR MARKET IN ALBANIA

S. Jorgji (Fortuzi)

Polytechnic University of Tirana

Tirana, Albania

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Abstract

This article aims to highlight the consequences of employee turnover using the Albanian working environment as a subject of study.

To begin with, the turnover of employees is a serious problem for many companies and even more so in the conditions where the labor market tends to change at a fast and continuous rate, so the study is considered important. The research was done by means of a questionnaire where the people who completed it were selected by the most suitable sampling method. The questionnaire had in total 163 responses. The findings indicated that this study aims to understand the causes of employee turnover and retention strategies in an organization. The main findings of the research show that employees have several reasons for leaving their workplace, including finding a better job, lack of opportunities to advance in higher positions and salary since they are not acquiring new skills from of the organization.

The purpose of this study is to determine the reasons that lead employees to turnover as well as the factors that lead to turnover in the Albanian environment. Firstly, the specific objectives in this article are to find the reasons why employees leave work and secondly to identify the main influencing factors.

Keywords: Employee Turnover, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment.

INTRODUCTION

The structure of the labor market in Albania has undergone significant changes in recent years. Employees leave organizations for various reasons, and this turnover has a major impact on the organization. For example, companies need to hire and train new employees, allowing them sufficient time to become productive. Additionally, employee turnover is costly for organizations in terms of replacement expenses for new hires. Some find new jobs, some return to school, some follow a partner who has been transferred to another city, while others retire or leave due to current conflicts. Some employees may be laid off, or they may win the lottery and decide they no longer need a job. All these are examples of turnover, but not all have the same value for the organization. Organizations have paid significant attention to employee turnover because it has major implications for them.

As a result, organizations need to understand their employees' needs, enabling them to adopt strategies to improve employee performance and reduce turnover. Therefore, there are several employee retention strategies, such as good management systems, offering train-

ing, job involvement, job satisfaction, providing rewards and benefits, high job engagement, good management systems, and high employee involvement.

Furthermore, other factors have been identified, such as career advancement and development, high salary levels, interpersonal conflicts with colleagues, poor human resource policies, and personal reasons that cause the desire for change.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a questionnaire to gather data, focusing on demographic factors such as age, gender, and education, alongside exploring aspects like job role and experience. The findings revealed significant insights into the workforce demographics and their perspectives on employment.

In this section, we will focus on the results and findings of the questionnaire, starting with demographic factors such as age, gender, education, as well as factors such as experience and job role.

Respondents answered questions about the field in which they worked, and below we see the table. It should be noted that there may be several alternatives, as the question did not require a single choice.

Fig 1. Field of employment

Age of the respondents

The study asked the questioner about their age. According to the table above, the highest percentage is 24-30 (47.2%), followed by 31-40 (23.9%), 18-23 (17.2%), 41-55 (16%), and 55+ (just 3 questions). The age of 55 will not be addressed in future investigations because the sample size appears to be small.

Fig 2 Age of the respondents

In this section, respondents have answered about their gender. The majority were females, accounting for 67.5%, while males accounted for 32.5%. This could

indicate that females had greater access to this questionnaire, or it might suggest that males are less interested in completing online surveys. However, this issue is not the subject of this study.

Table 1

Gender of respondents Educational Level		
Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Female (F)	110	67.5
Male (M)	53	32.5
Total	163	100%

Respondents were asked to provide their level of education. According to the table, respondents with an 8-year education level were 0%, those with secondary

education were 3.7%, while higher education was predominant, with 62% of respondents having completed higher education and 34% having completed postgraduate education.

Table 2

Education level Reasons for Leaving the Job

Educational level	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary (primary)	0	0
High school	6	3.7
Bachelor	101	62
Master or Doctoral	56	34.4%
Total	163	100%

This has been one of the most important questions of this study, and below we see some interesting results. The first response is the desire for a better job opportunity, which had a frequency of 42, followed by the

lack of opportunities for advancement in the job, followed by salary, and "I wasn't gaining new skills".

Fig 3 Reasons of leaving work

MAIN PART

The dynamic nature of the labor market in Albania has undergone substantial transformations in recent years. Employee turnover, a prevalent phenomenon, significantly impacts organizations. This turnover necessitates the recruitment and training of new employees, incurring costs for the organization. Various reasons contribute to employee turnover, such as seeking better job opportunities, pursuing education, relocating due to personal reasons, or conflicts within the workplace. These factors highlight the complexities and challenges associated with managing employee turnover effectively.

The analysis of demographic data revealed that respondents primarily belonged to the age group of 24-30, with females comprising the majority of participants. Regarding educational background, a significant proportion of respondents had completed higher education or postgraduate studies.

One of the pivotal findings of the study pertains to the reasons for leaving a job. The desire for better job opportunities emerged as the predominant factor, followed by the lack of advancement prospects within the

organization, salary concerns, and a perceived stagnation in skill development. These findings underscore the multifaceted nature of employee turnover and the diverse factors influencing employees' decisions to leave their current employment.

FINDINGS

To summarize, the results of personnel turnover are not necessarily negative, the outcomes of employee turnover can be both negative and positive, but they can also be advantageous and favorable. Table 3. When there is a significant amount of turnover, confidence can decrease as well as there may be pressure on the company's remaining employees to find the best candidates for open positions or, in some situations, not fill all the positions. It must be acknowledged and recognized that elevated levels of education affected and influenced the value of the employees' labor market. Fig 3

Consequently, as a result circulating aspirations and goals increased among those individuals who had encountered emotions of unfair and unequal justice, as well as people who were responsible for the other gender. In addition, the duration of employment influences

employees' feelings and attitudes toward their occupations.

The primary reason for quitting is for a better job position, which may be 42, subsequently followed by a lack of possibilities for advancement and progress in the working environment, followed by income, and "I wasn't gaining new skills". Graph 5.

Finally, respondents would avoid jobs where employees left for higher compensation and better career opportunities.

In conclusion, employee turnover presents both challenges and opportunities for organizations. While it can lead to disruptions and increased recruitment costs, it also offers a chance for organizational growth and adaptation. Understanding the underlying reasons for employee turnover is crucial for implementing effective retention strategies and fostering a positive work environment conducive to employee satisfaction and productivity.

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